

MUNICIPALITY OF WEST BENGAL: A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO 74 TH CONSTITUTIONAL AMENDMENTS IN 1992

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Abstract

An autonomous institution within a municipal or urban area is known as a Municipality. For a long period, municipalities in West Bengal were established and governed under the Bengal Municipality Act, 1932. As this administrative framework a relic of the colonial era proved unable to adapt to the changed circumstances of the modern day, the Left Front government of West Bengal amended the Bengal Municipality Act twice in succession, in 1980 and 1982. However, due to certain lingering flaws, the West Bengal Legislative Assembly once again passed the 'West Bengal Municipal Bill, 1993' on July 21, 1993. Upon receiving the President's assent towards the end of May 1994, the Bill became an Act and came into force on June 1. It is pertinent to note that this new Act was enacted in consonance with the 74th Constitutional Amendment Act (1992).

Key- Words: *West Bengal Municipal Bill, Municipality, Urban, Powers and Functions etc.*

Introduction:

This 74 th Amendment Act holds significant importance in the realm of urban administration in India. Through this amendment, Part IX 'A' was inserted into the Constitution following Part IX. Matters such as the composition, tenure, powers, and responsibilities of municipalities are outlined in this Amendment Act. Consequently, local autonomous institutions in urban areas have been elevated to the status of constitutional bodies, akin to the Central and State governments. Other salient features of this Amendment Act are as follows:

- (1) The State Legislature may, through legislation, make provisions for the constitution of Ward Committees within municipalities.

(2) At the time of constituting a municipality, the State Legislature may, at its discretion, nominate a few individuals possessing experience or specialized knowledge in municipal administration to serve as members of the municipality. However, these members shall not possess any voting rights.

(3) Provisions must be made in every municipality for the reservation of seats for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and women. One-third of the total number of members belonging to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes must be reserved for women of those respective communities. One-third of the total number of members of the Municipality (including seats reserved for women belonging to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes) must be reserved for women.

(4) This Amendment Act also provides for the constitution of a Planning Commission, the function of which shall be to give concrete shape to the plans formulated by the Municipality and to draft plans for the development of the district.

(5) Through this amendment, the Twelfth Schedule has been added to the Constitution. This Schedule enumerates 18 subjects that are to be administered by the Municipality.

(6) Elected representatives to the Lok Sabha and the Rajya Sabha whose constituencies fall within the jurisdiction of a municipality shall serve as members of the respective municipality.

(6) In accordance with Article 243Q of the Constitution, the establishment of a Nagar Panchayat, a Municipality, and a Corporation is mandatory in every state of the Indian Union. Municipalities are to be constituted in smaller towns, Corporations in larger cities, and Nagar Panchayats in areas situated in the transitional zone between rural and urban settlements.

(7) Provision has been made for the constitution of a Finance Commission to assess the financial position of the Municipality and to make recommendations to the State Government in this regard.

Structure of Municipality:

The structure of the Municipality, as outlined in the new West Bengal Municipal Act (1993) which was enacted in consonance with the 84th Constitutional Amendment Act is discussed below:

Category A: Municipalities with a population exceeding 200,000 and comprising 35 wards

Category B: Municipalities with a population ranging from 150,000 to 200,000 and comprising 30 wards.

Category C: Municipalities with a population ranging from 75,000 to 150,000 and comprising 25 wards.

Category D: Municipalities with a population ranging from 25,000 to 75,000 and comprising 20 wards.

Category E: Municipalities with a population of up to 25,000 and comprising 15 wards.

Under the new Act, members of the municipality are referred to as 'Councillors' rather than 'Commissioners.' They are elected for a term of five years through universal adult suffrage. To be elected as a Councillor, a candidate must: (i) be at least 21 years of age; (ii) be an elector (voter) of the concerned municipal area; (iii) not be a member of any other municipality or municipal institution; and (iv) not hold any office of profit under the municipality. Provisions have been made to reserve seats for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes in proportion to the total population of the respective municipal area. Furthermore, the Act stipulates that at least one-third of the total number of seats in a municipality (including seats reserved for women belonging to SC and ST) must be reserved for women.

According to the new Act, three distinct Municipal Authorities have been constituted to execute and manage the functions of municipalities in West Bengal: (1) The Municipality (Board of Councillors), (2) The Chairman-in-Council, and (3) The Chairman.

(1) The Municipality (Board of Councillors): The body formed by comprising the elected Councillors of the municipality, along with individuals nominated by the State Government who possess knowledge and experience in municipal administration, is known as the Municipality (or the Board of Councillors). The nominated members of the Board of Councillors do not possess voting rights. According to the new legislation, a specific proportion of the seats for elected councillors in every municipality is reserved for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. Furthermore, one-third of the total number of seats in the municipality (including those reserved for women belonging to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes) is reserved for women.

(2) Chairman-in-Council: The Chairman-in-Council consists of the Chairman, the Vice-Chairman, and a specific number of members drawn from among the councillors of the municipality—specifically 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 member(s) for municipalities classified under categories A, B, C, D, and E, respectively. Within 30 days of assuming office, the Chairman shall appoint a Vice-Chairman and the other members from among the councillors of the municipality. The Chairman-in-Council of the municipality bears the responsibility for, and

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exercises authority over, all administrative functions. The Chairman-in-Council remains accountable to the Council of Councillors or to the municipality as a whole—for all its activities.

(3) Chairman: During their very first session, the members of the Council of Councillors elect one person from among themselves to serve as the Chairman. Should the Council fail to elect a Chairman, the State Government may appoint one of the councillors to the position. The Chairman serves as the 'Chief Executive' of the municipality. His tenure of office is five years; however, he may voluntarily resign from his post prior to the completion of this term. Alternatively, he may be removed from office through a specific procedural mechanism. The Chairman is deemed removed if a proposal for his removal—introduced during a special meeting convened at the written request of one-third of the total elected members of the municipality is adopted by a majority vote of the elected members present.

The primary functions of the Chairman are: (1) To appoint the Vice-Chairman and other members of the Chairman-in-Council, and to allocate portfolios among them; (2) To preside over the meetings of the Council of Councillors and the Chairman-in-Council; (3) As the administrative head of the Municipality, to implement the decisions adopted during the meetings of the Council of Councillors and the Chairman-in-Council; (4) To determine the agenda for the meetings of the Council of Councillors and the Chairman-in-Council; (5) To issue directives for the execution of any task deemed necessary on an emergency basis, and to subsequently bring the relevant matter to the notice of the Council of Councillors and the Chairman-in-Council; (6) To preserve all papers, files, and documents of the Municipality; (7) To coordinate the various development-oriented activities of the Municipality; additionally, to maintain liaison with various developmental agencies operating under the State Government and the District Administration; (8) Finally, to discharge such other duties as may be directed by the State Government, among others. In the absence of the Chairman, the Vice-Chairman performs all the functions of the Chairman.

Committee System:

The new Municipal Act provides for six types of committees, namely: (1) Borough Committee, (2) Ward Committee, (3) Standing Committee, (4) Heritage Conservation Committee, (5) Special Committee, and (6) Joint Committee. In any Municipality with a population of 300,000 or more, the municipal wards are divided into five boroughs either during the first session following the election of members or as soon thereafter as practicable such that each borough comprises at least six contiguous wards. A Borough Committee is

constituted for each borough. The elected Councillors representing the wards that constitute a specific borough serve as members of the corresponding Borough Committee.

Ward Committee: The West Bengal Municipal (Amendment) Act of 1997 stipulates that a committee must mandatorily be constituted in every ward of the Municipality. Each Ward Committee consists of the elected Councillor of the respective ward along with several other members. These additional members are nominated jointly by the Councillor of the concerned ward and the Council of Councillors. The number of such additional members varies in proportion to the population of the ward. A Ward Committee may consist of a minimum of 7 and a maximum of 17 members, in addition to the Chairperson. Among these additional members, 2 or 3 are drawn from the Community Development Society, while the remaining members are nominated from among the residents of the respective ward—including social workers, educationists, doctors, engineers, athletes, women, and individuals belonging to backward classes. The elected Councillor's of the respective ward serves as the Chairperson of the Ward Committee. Within 15 days of the formation of the Ward Committee, the Chairperson convenes the committee's inaugural meeting; during this meeting, one individual is elected from among the committee members to serve as the Member Secretary. Subsequent meetings are convened by this Member Secretary. The Ward Committee is required to convene a meeting at least once every month. Every resident of the ward is entitled to participate in the committee's annual meeting, held in October or November, as well as in the half-yearly meeting held in June. During the annual meeting, reports detailing the committee's activities and financial matters for the preceding year are presented for discussion.

Functions of the Ward Committee: The primary function of the Ward Committee is to ensure that municipal operations within the respective ward are being executed properly, and to oversee other matters related to the municipality, such as: (a) supervising the cleaning of roads, drains, and the removal of garbage, and informing the Councillors as necessary; (b) monitoring road repairs, ensuring proper drainage, and verifying the functional status of tube wells, drinking water pipelines, etc., while bringing these matters to the Councillor's attention in a timely manner; (c) keeping a watch for any activities that violate municipal laws—such as unauthorized construction or the encroachment upon municipal property; and (d) monitoring for any irregularities within public utility sectors, including parks, playgrounds, libraries, piped water supply, and street lighting keeping a watch over such matters; (e) raising public grievances and complaints at the appropriate forums; (f) assisting in the proper

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implementation of vaccination drives, disease prevention programs, literacy campaigns, poverty alleviation schemes, etc.; (g) presenting the committee's activities before the members present at the annual ward meeting, explaining the status of unfinished tasks, and so forth.

Standing Committee: Under the West Bengal Municipal (Amendment) Act of 2002, the formation of six Standing Committees has been made mandatory for every municipality. These Standing Committees are: (1) Standing Committee on Finance and Resource Mobilisation; (2) Standing Committee on Public Works; (3) Standing Committee on Health, Education, and Urban Poverty Alleviation; (4) Standing Committee on Public Health and Sanitation; (5) Standing Committee on Solid Waste Management; and (6) Standing Committee on Water Supply. Each municipality employs a staff comprising, among others, a Municipal Secretary, an Executive Officer, a Health Officer, one or more Sanitary Inspectors, a Head Clerk, a Head Assistant, an Accountant, an Office Superintendent, a Finance Officer, a Medical Officer, an Assistant Engineer, one or more Sub-Assistant Engineers, a Surveyor, and a Draftsman. Under the new legislation, the tenure of the members of a municipality has been fixed at five years. However, should the need arise, the State Government may extend the tenure of a municipality by one year; alternatively, prior to the expiration of its term, the government may dissolve any municipality and appoint an Administrator to oversee its affairs.

Powers and Functions of the Municipality:

With the objective of ensuring the holistic development of its jurisdiction, a municipality is required to perform a wide array of functions. The powers and functions of the municipality are delineated in Sections 63 through 66, located within Chapter VI of the new Municipal Act. The functions of a municipality are primarily of three types: (1) Mandatory functions, (2) Discretionary functions, and (3) Functions imposed by the State Government.

(1) Notable among the mandatory functions are: (a) Construction and maintenance of roads; (b) Supply of drinking water; (c) Provision of sewerage and drainage systems; (d) Street lighting; (e) Adoption of preventive measures against infectious diseases and epidemics; (f) Prevention of environmental pollution; (g) Creation and maintenance of gardens, parks, etc.; (h) Curbing unauthorized construction; (i) Urban and slum development; (j) Registration of births and deaths; (k) Disposal of unclaimed bodies and removal of dead animals; (l) Demolition of hazardous structures; (m) Preservation of properties owned by the municipality; (n) Control of all forms of pollution; (o) Arranging for proper training of

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municipal staff; (p) Identifying unhygienic localities and improving their environmental conditions; (q) Enhancing public immunity through vaccination; (r) Cooperating with utility agencies operating within the area, and preserving martyrs' memorials and sites of historical significance; (s) Evicting illegal encroachments from roads, bridges, and similar public spaces; (t) Observing days of national importance; (u) Maintaining records and statistics regarding the administrative operations of the municipality; etc.

(2) Notable among the discretionary functions are: (a) the construction and maintenance of shops, markets, cremation grounds, burial grounds, rest houses, libraries, Dharamshalas (pilgrim rest houses), warehouses, etc.; (b) undertaking relief measures in instances of floods, famines, etc.; (c) the construction and maintenance of child welfare centers, hospitals, maternity homes, etc.; (d) making provisions for adult education and non-formal education; (e) encouraging the cooperative movement; (f) promoting small-scale and cottage industries; (g) arranging for housing for the elderly, orphans, and the homeless; (h) constructing low-cost housing for people belonging to backward classes within the municipal area; (i) promoting science and technology; (j) raising social awareness regarding public health, the environment, human rights, and other issues through the organization of meetings, conferences, seminars, etc.; (k) encouraging the increased adoption of biogas and other non-conventional energy sources; (l) taking appropriate measures for the production of organic manure from waste materials; (m) organizing fairs and exhibitions; (n) felicitating distinguished personalities; (o) taking measures to curb drug addiction; (p) the reclamation of fallow land and social forestry, etc.

(3) Notable among the functions mandated by the State Government are: (a) urban and rural development planning; (b) the regulation and distribution of food and food supplies; (c) forestation; (d) civil defence; (e) the welfare of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes; (f) health and family welfare; (g) sports and youth welfare; (h) environmental protection and development; (i) fire services, etc. If the State Government issues directives to execute any one or all of these tasks, the municipalities are bound to comply. However, the State Government shall provide the necessary funds and personnel required to execute these tasks.

Sources of Income: To efficiently execute the aforementioned activities which require substantial financial resources municipalities generate funds from various sources. Grants or financial assistance provided by the State and Central governments constitute the primary source of municipal income. However, the State or Central government may stipulate the specific purposes for which such grants or aid are to be utilized, as well as the manner in

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which they are to be expended. The second most significant source of municipal revenue is the funds collected through various taxes and fees; these include taxes levied on land and buildings, vehicles, ferries and bridges, trades and professions, and advertisements (excluding those published in newspapers); as well as taxes on entertainment, fees charged for circuses, Jatras (folk theatre), fairs, and similar events held within municipal limits, and various license fees. The State government often imposes taxes on the registration of smaller vehicles, automobiles, animal-drawn carts, two-wheeled handcarts, rickshaws, and similar conveyances; these taxes are collected by the municipality. Occasionally, the municipality may impound unregistered vehicles and impose fines, thereby generating additional revenue. Furthermore, municipalities derive some income from sources such as markets and rest houses. Finally, with the prior approval of the State government, a municipality may secure loans from various financial institutions or nationalized banks. In such instances, the State government often serves as the guarantor.

The Control exercised by the State Government over the Municipalities:

One of the main conditions for the success of municipalities as local autonomous institutions is an environment in which they can work free from government control. Accordingly, the Municipal Act of 1993 has given much more power to the municipalities than before. But despite this, the municipalities of West Bengal are still bound by various government controls. This control is mainly of three types. Namely-

(a) Legal control: The municipalities of West Bengal have been formed under the Act made by the West Bengal Legislative Assembly and they have to work under the laws and instructions of the State Government. The municipalities do not have the power to do anything beyond those laws.

(b) Financial control: One of the main tools for establishing state government control over the municipalities is the provision of financial grants by the State Government. The amount of money collected from the municipalities' own sources of income is so small that it is entirely spent on paying salaries to employees and other incidental expenses. As a result, the municipalities have to depend on government grants for adopting and implementing development programs. Needless to say, the state government is able to control the municipalities by taking advantage of this dependence. An auditor is appointed to examine the income and expenditure of the municipality. If his report mentions any financial irregularities against a municipality, the state government can take appropriate action against the municipality concerned.

(c) Administrative control: Administrative control by the state government can be effective in various ways. First, the state government can direct the municipality or any department of the municipality to submit letters, documents, etc. to the government or to submit a report on any matter. Needless to say, it is mandatory for the municipal institution to comply with these instructions. Second, if it is considered that any proposal adopted by the municipality is not legal, the state government can cancel that proposal. Third, if the state government directs the municipal institutions to perform any work, the municipal institutions are bound to comply with that instruction. Fourthly, the District Magistrate or the Sub-Divisional Magistrate or any Director of the Local Bodies may at any time inspect the progress of the work of the Municipality, or may inspect any department of the Municipality. In such a case, it is mandatory for the Chairman or any Municipal Officer to furnish the documents, records, files, etc. as directed by the aforesaid authority. Fifthly, the appointment, salary, allowances, leave and other conditions of service of the employees are determined by the State Government. Finally, the biggest tool for controlling the Municipalities is that the State Government can dissolve any Municipal Institution on the pretext of administrative inefficiency and appoint an Administrator. However, the State Government has to form a new Municipality by holding re-election within 6 months from the date of dissolution.

Evaluation: Various allegations regarding shortcomings and irregularities are frequently levelled against municipal institutions in West Bengal. Firstly, the majority of municipal councillors lack the requisite competence and experience essential for effective administrative functioning. Secondly, the municipal administrative system suffers significantly because councillors are not full-time employees and, furthermore, often lack formal training. Thirdly, allegations of corruption and factionalism are also frequently raised against municipal councillors. Fourthly, excessive government control acts as a major impediment to the successful operation of municipal institutions. Above all, according to critics, municipalities have effectively transformed into focal points of partisan politics. Consequently, periods of election are often characterized by intense inter-party rivalry and outbreaks of violence. Elected representatives tend to be more preoccupied with matters of political gain than with the provision of municipal services. Despite these shortcomings, the municipalities of West Bengal continue to play an exemplary role, remaining steadfast in their commitment to the goal of democratic decentralization.

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